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DEEP LEARNING-POWERED FORECASTING OF CRUDE OIL PRICES: CAPTURING NONLINEAR MARKET DYNAMICS

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ABSTRACT

Crude oil price forecasting is of paramount importance for various stakeholders, including policymakers, investors, and businesses. Understanding and predicting crude oil prices help in making informed decisions, managing risks, and planning economic strategies. The history of crude oil price forecasting dates back to the early days of oil exploration and production. Traditional methods for crude oil price forecasting often rely on linear models, which assume a constant relationship between variables. Linear regression, autoregressive integrated moving average, and exponential smoothing are commonly used techniques. While these methods work well for stable and linear relationships, they fail to capture the intricate patterns and nonlinearities present in crude oil price data, especially when influenced by a multitude of factors, including geopolitical tensions, natural disasters, economic indicators, technological advancements, and government policies. These factors interact in complex and nonlinear ways, making it challenging to capture their impact using linear models. Nonlinear dynamics modeling is essential because it allows researchers and analysts to explore the intricate relationships between these factors and crude oil prices, considering the nonlinear patterns and dependencies that exist in the data. Therefore, given historical data on crude oil prices and various influencing factors, this research aims to develop a predictive model that can capture the nonlinear relationships and patterns in the data. The goal is to accurately forecast future crude oil prices under different scenarios, considering the dynamic interplay of geopolitical events, market sentiment, economic indicators, and supply-demand dynamics. The proposed model is capable of adapting to changing market conditions and provide reliable forecasts, helping stakeholders make informed decisions and mitigate risks associated with crude oil price fluctuations.

KEYWORDS : Crude Oil Price Forecasting, Nonlinear Dynamics, Time Series Analysis, Energy Market Modeling, Economic Forecasting

1. INTRODUCTION

The crude oil price movements are subject to diverse influencing factors. The dynamic complicated interactions among these factors result in the mysterious behavior of the crude oil price movement, whose characterization and prediction remained one of the most interesting and intriguing research issues in the economic and financial analysis field. Recently numerous empirical studies have revealed the nonlinear nature of economic and

financial data, where traditional methods such as linear prediction methods are not able to analyze the complex nonlinear dynamics involved [1]. [2] used the Qual VAR model to model the nonlinear autocorrelation characteristics of WTI crude oil price changes and forecast its future movement. They found that the Qual VAR model outperforms the benchmark Random Walk and VAR model. [3] proposed a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) with threshold effect to model hidden factors

influencing the crude oil price movement. They demonstrated that the proposed models outperform the ARMA model, in h-day ahead forecasting exercise. On the other hand, the Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) based approaches received more and more research interests. [4] used the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to forecast the crude oil indices. [5] proposed a Genetic Algorithm optimized Neural Network model to forecast the crude oil price fluctuations. They showed this evolutionary neural network model brings statistically significant performance improvement. [6] provided a comprehensive survey on the AI and ML based crude oil forecasting models.

The deep learning model is a new artificial intelligence paradigm developed beyond the neural network. It has become a popular phenomenon in the computer science and engineering fields such as image recognition, text classification and speech recognition recently. For example, [7] proposed HMM-DNN model for speech synthesis method. In addition to the HMM-DNN model, the CNN model and the RNN model are also applied to the construction of speech recognition models. However, the deep learning model has only been introduced to the financial field quite recently. There are some very early exploratory attempts. For example, [8] proposed a deep learning hierarchical decision model and used it to construct new portfolio with the desired level of performance. Empirical studies show that the proposed model achieves the superior performance. [9] predicted the real estate price by combining the Boltzmann machine with the genetic algorithm. [10] applied the convolution neural network to the biological aspects of DNA-protein transcription prediction. [11] used the deep belief network model to predict the short-term power load in Macedonia from 2008 to 2014. The empirical results showed that the deep belief network model has obvious advantages compared with the traditional forecasting models.

In this project, we propose a new Deep learning-based hybrid crude oil price forecasting methodology to model the nonlinear dynamics involved in the crude oil price movement and forecast its future movement at higher level of accuracy. Considering both the linear and non-linear characteristics of historical data, we integrate the prediction results of the ARMA model and the prediction results of the deep learning model. Empirical studies have been conducted using the major crude oil prices to evaluate the performance of the proposed model. The superior performance of the crude oil price forecasting model using the deep belief network and recurrent neural network provide the empirical evidence that the market is inefficient in the regional and submarkets. Work in this paper shows methodologically the merit of the deep learning model in tracking and capturing the nonlinearity and dynamic crude oil price movement. When analytic solutions are lacking, it would provide the best approximation to the nonlinear dynamics in the crude oil price movement. It contributes to the literature by providing a new methodology on how the deep learning model can be used to improve the crude oil forecasting accuracy.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Monthly Energy Review; U.S. Energy Information Administration. Available online: <https://www.eia.gov/totalenergy/data/monthly/index.php> (accessed on 10 February 2020).

Note 1. Merchandise Trade Value. Imports data presented are based on the customs values. Those values do not include insurance and freight and are consequently lower than the cost, insurance, and freight (CIF) values, which are also reported by the Bureau of the Census. All exports data, and imports data through 1980, are on a free alongside ship (f.a.s.) basis. "Balance" is exports minus imports; a positive balance indicates a surplus trade value and a negative balance indicates a deficit trade value. "Energy" includes mineral fuels, lubricants, and related material.

“Non-Energy Balance” and “Total Merchandise” include foreign exports (i.e., re-exports) and nonmonetary gold and U.S. Department of Defense Grant- Aid shipments. The “Non-Energy Balance” is calculated by subtracting the “Energy” from the “Total Merchandise Balance.” “Imports” consist of government and nongovernment shipments of merchandise into the 50 states, the District of Columbia, Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and the U.S. Foreign Trade Zones. They reflect the total arrival from foreign countries of merchandise that immediately entered consumption channels, warehouses, the Foreign Trade Zones, or the Strategic Petroleum Reserve. They exclude shipments between the United States, Puerto Rico, and U.S. possessions, shipments to U.S. Armed Forces and diplomatic missions abroad for their own use, U.S. goods returned to the United States by its Armed Forces, and in-transit shipments. Note 2. Non-Combustion Use of Fossil Fuels. Most fossil fuels consumed in the United States and elsewhere are combusted to produce heat and power. However, some are used directly for non-combustion use as construction materials, chemical feedstocks, lubricants, solvents, and waxes. For example, coal tars from coal coke manufacturing are used as feedstock in the chemical industry, for metallurgical work, and in anti-dandruff shampoos; natural gas is used to make nitrogenous fertilizers and as chemical feedstocks; asphalt and road oil are used for roofing and paving; hydrocarbon gas liquids are used to create intermediate products that are used in making plastics; lubricants, including motor oil and greases, are used in vehicles and various industrial processes; petrochemical feedstocks are used to make plastics, synthetic fabrics, and related products.

[2] **Saggu, A.; Anukoonwattaka, W. Commodity Price Crash: Risks to Exports and Economic Growth in Asia-Pacific LDCs and LLDCs. United Nations ESCAP Trade Insights 2015, 6, 2617542.**

This issue of the Trade Insights series identifies Asia-Pacific LDCs and LLDCs with export-portfolios and economies which are at greatest risk from the recent collapse in global commodity prices. Asia-Pacific LDCs and LLDCs account for less than 2% of global commodity exports and just 7% of Asia-Pacific commodity exports; however many these economies have export-portfolios which are highly concentrated in one or two major commodities: mainly crude oil, natural gas, aluminum, iron ore/steel, cotton and copper. This note finds that economic growth is at significant risk from changes in commodity prices across many Asia-Pacific LDCs and LLDCs, particularly in fuel-exporting economies and metal and mineral exporting economies.

[3] **Chatzis, P.S.; Siakoulis, V.; Petropoulos, A.; Stavroulakis, E.; Vlachogiannakis, N. Forecasting stock market crisis events using deep and statistical machine learning techniques. Expert Syst. Appl. 2018, 112, 353–371.**

Predictions of stock and foreign exchange (Forex) have always been a hot and profitable area of study. Deep learning applications have been proven to yield better accuracy and return in the field of financial prediction and forecasting. In this survey, we selected papers from the Digital Bibliography & Library Project (DBLP) database for comparison and analysis. We classified papers according to different deep learning methods, which included Convolutional neural network (CNN); Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM); Deep neural network (DNN); Recurrent Neural Network (RNN); Reinforcement Learning; and other deep learning methods such as Hybrid Attention Networks (HAN), self-paced learning mechanism (NLP), and Wavenet. Furthermore, this paper reviews the dataset, variable, model, and results of each article. The survey used presents the results through the most used performance metrics: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error

(MSE), accuracy, Sharpe ratio, and return rate. We identified that recent models combining LSTM with other methods, for example, DNN, are widely researched. Reinforcement learning and other deep learning methods yielded great returns and performances. We conclude that, in recent years, the trend of using deep-learning-based methods for financial modeling is rising exponentially.

[4] Koch, N.; Fuss, S.; Grosjean, G.; Edenhofer, O. Causes of the EU ETS price drop: Recession, CDM, renewable policies or a bit of everything?—New evidence. *Energy Policy* 2014, 73, 676–685

This paper examines the usefulness of asset prices in predicting the beginnings of recessions in the G-7 countries. It finds that equity/house price drops have a substantial marginal effect on the likelihood of a new recession. Increased market uncertainty, which is a second-moment variable associated with equity price changes, is also a useful predictor of new recessions in these countries. These findings are robust to the inclusion of the term spread and oil prices. The new recession forecasting performance of our baseline model is superior to that of a similar model estimated over all recession and expansion periods, highlighting a difference between the probabilities of a new recession versus a continuing recession.

[5] Baumeister, C.; Kilian, L. Forecasting the real price of oil in a changing world: A forecast combination approach. *J. Bus. Econ. Stat.* 2015, 33, 338–351.

The U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) regularly publishes monthly and quarterly forecasts of the price of crude oil for horizons up to 2 years, which are widely used by practitioners. Traditionally, such out-of-sample forecasts have been largely judgmental, making them difficult to replicate and justify. An alternative is the use of real-time econometric oil price forecasting models. We investigate the merits of constructing combinations of six such models. Forecast combinations have received little attention in the oil price forecasting literature to date. We

demonstrate that over the last 20 years suitably constructed real-time forecast combinations would have been systematically more accurate than the no-change forecast at horizons up to 6 quarters or 18 months. The MSPE reductions may be as high as 12% and directional accuracy as high as 72%. The gains in accuracy are robust over time. In contrast, the EIA oil price forecasts not only tend to be less accurate than no-change forecasts, but are much less accurate than our preferred forecast combination. Moreover, including EIA forecasts in the forecast combination systematically lowers the accuracy of the combination forecast. We conclude that suitably constructed forecast combinations should replace traditional judgmental forecasts of the price of oil.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Python code is a GUI application built using the Tkinter library for forecasting crude oil prices

Importing Libraries: The code begins by importing necessary libraries such as Tkinter for GUI, Matplotlib for plotting graphs, NumPy, Pandas for data manipulation, os for file operations, Keras and TensorFlow for deep learning, and statsmodels for ARIMA modeling.

Setting up the GUI: The main GUI window is created using `tkinter.Tk()`. Title and geometry are set for the main window.

Global Variables:

1. `filename`: Used to store the path of the uploaded dataset file.
2. `batch_size`, `epochs`, `timesteps`: Parameters for deep learning models.
3. `lstm_accuracy`, `arma_accuracy`: Variables to store accuracy values.

Function Definitions:

1. `upload()`: Allows users to upload a dataset file.
2. `get_train_length()`: Calculates the length of the training set based on batch size and test percentage.
3. `runLSTM()`: Executes LSTM model for crude oil price forecasting.

4. runARMA(): Executes ARIMA model for crude oil price forecasting.
5. graph(): Plots a bar graph comparing LSTM and ARIMA accuracies.
6. exit(): Closes the GUI window.

GUI Components: Labels, buttons, and text fields are created and placed using the Label() and Button() functions. These components are configured with specific text, fonts, colors, and positions on the GUI window. Buttons are associated with their respective functions for uploading data, running LSTM and ARIMA models, plotting accuracy graph, and exiting the application.

Main Loop: The main.mainloop() function runs the GUI application, waiting for user interactions.

GUI Styling: Fonts, colors, and sizes are configured for various GUI components to enhance readability and aesthetics.

Model Execution: The LSTM and ARIMA models are implemented for forecasting crude oil prices based on the uploaded dataset or generated data. Accuracy metrics are calculated and displayed in the GUI text field. Predicted prices are displayed along with the current price inputted by the user.

Graph Plotting: The accuracy of LSTM and ARIMA models is plotted on a bar graph for comparison.

File Operations: Temporary files are created and used for data manipulation or model input.

Long short-term memory (LSTM) RNN in TensorFlow

Long short-term memory (LSTM) is an artificial recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture used in the field of deep learning. It was proposed in 1997 by **Sepp Hochreiter** and **Jürgen Schmidhuber**. Unlike standard feed-forward neural networks, LSTM has feedback connections. It can process not only single data points (such as images) but also entire sequences of data (such as speech or video).

For example, LSTM is an application to tasks such as unsegmented, **connected handwriting recognition**, or **speech recognition**.

A general LSTM unit is composed of a cell, an input gate, an output gate, and a forget gate. The cell remembers values over arbitrary time intervals, and three gates regulate the flow of information into and out of the cell. LSTM is well-suited to classify, process, and predict the time series given of unknown duration.

Figure 1: LSTM cell.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The project employs 2 deep learning algorithms such as LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory Network), and ARMA to forecast crude oil prices. LSTM algorithm is a deep learning famous algorithms used to train and predict any kind of data such as voice recognition, image classification or data classification, this algorithm consist of three layers called input, output, forget layer and at input layer algorithm will read features from dataset and find out best features and saved that best features in output layer and this process continue to filter features between input and output layer and if best output found then assign it current output and old output will be assigned to forgot layer. Final filtered features will be used to train model. While prediction algorithm accept test data and then apply that test data on train model to predict accurate class to which this test data belongs.

ARMA algorithm will also use for same training and testing model but its accuracy of prediction is less compare to LSTM.

In the project we are using historical crude oil prices from QUANDL website as dataset and this dataset saved inside 'dataset' folder. This dataset contains two values such as DATE and price value. See below screen of dataset values

Screen shots

Figure 6

Figure 2 Upload Crude Oil Dataset

Figure 7

Figure 3 Uploading Dataset

Figure 8

Figure 4 Run Deep Learning LSTM Model & Forecast Price

Figure 9

Figure 5

Figure 10

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research proposes a deep learning-based crude oil price forecasting model that focuses on capturing the nonlinear dynamics inherent in crude oil price data. Traditional linear forecasting methods often

fall short in capturing the intricate relationships and nonlinear patterns present in the data, particularly when influenced by a multitude of complex factors. By leveraging advanced deep learning techniques, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, the proposed model aims to provide more accurate and reliable forecasts by considering the dynamic interplay of various influencing factors. The significance of accurate crude oil price forecasting cannot be overstated, as it has profound implications for policymakers, investors, businesses, and the global economy as a whole. Accurate forecasts enable stakeholders to make informed decisions, manage risks effectively, and plan strategies to navigate the volatile energy market landscape. By developing a model capable of capturing nonlinear dynamics, this research contributes to enhancing the understanding and prediction of crude oil prices, thereby empowering stakeholders to mitigate risks and seize opportunities in an increasingly complex and dynamic environment.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Shen, J. Chao, J. Zhao, Forecasting exchange rate using deep belief networks and conjugate gradient method, *Neurocomputing* 167 (2015) 243 – 253.
- [2] R. Gupta, M. Wohar, Forecasting oil and stock returns with a qual var using over 150 years off data, *Energy Economics* 62 (2017) 181–186.
- [3] D. M. Zhu, W. K. Ching, R. J. Elliott, T. K. Siu, L. M. Zhang, Hidden markov models with threshold effects and their applications to oil price forecasting, *Journal of Industrial and Management Optimization* 13 (2) (2017) 757–773.
- [4] J. Wang, J. Wang, Forecasting energy market indices with recurrent neural networks: Case study of crude oil price fluctuations, *Energy* 102 (2016) 365–374.
- [5] H. Chiroma, S. Abdulkareem, T. Herawan, Evolutionary neural network model for west texas intermediate crude oil price prediction, *Applied Energy* 142 (2015) 266 – 273.
- [6] H. Chiroma, S. Abdul-kareem, A. S. M. Noor, A. I. Abubakar, N. S. Safa, L. Shuib, M. F. Hamza, A. Y. Gital, T. Herawan, A review on artificial intelligence methodologies for the forecasting of crude oil price, *Intelligent Automation and Soft Computing* 22 (3) (2016) 449–462.
- [7] Z. H. Ling, L. Deng, D. Yu, Modeling spectral envelopes using restricted boltzmann machines and deep belief networks for statistical parametric speech synthesis, *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing* 21 (10) (2013) 2129–2139.
- [8] J. B. Heaton, N. G. Polson, J. H. Witte, Deep learning for finance: deep portfolios, *Applied Stochastic Models in Business and Industry* 33 (1) (2017) 3–12.
- [9] M. H. Rafiei, H. Adeli, A novel machine learning model for estimation of sale prices of real estate units, *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management* 142 (2) (2016) 04015066.
- [10] H. Y. Zeng, M. D. Edwards, G. Liu, D. K. Gifford, Convolutional neural network architectures for predicting dna-protein binding, *Bioinformatics* 32 (12) (2016) 121–127.
- [11] A. Dedinec, S. Filiposka, A. Dedinec, L. Kocarev, Deep belief network based electricity load forecasting: An analysis of macedonian case, *Energy* 115, Part 3 (2016) 1688 – 1700, *Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems*.
- [12] G. E. Hinton, R. R. Salakhutdinov, Reducing the dimensionality of data with neural networks, *Science* 313 (5786) (2006) 504.
- [13] Y. Bengio, *Learning Deep Architectures for AI*, Now Publishers, 2009. [14] H. Lee, R. Grosse, R. Ranganath, A. Y. Ng, Convolutional deep belief networks for scalable unsupervised learning of hierarchical representations, in: *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2009, pp. 609 – 616.

- [14] G. E. Hinton, S. Osindero, Y. W. Teh, A fast learning algorithm for deep belief nets, *Neural Computation* 18 (7) (2014) 1527–1554.
- [15] I. Arel, D. C. Rose, T. P. Karnowski, Deep machine learning - a new frontier in artificial intelligence research [research frontier], *IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine* 5 (4) (2010) 13–18.
- [16] S. Hochreiter, J. Schmidhuber, Long short-term memory, *Neural Computation* 9 (8) (1997) 1735.
- [17] F. A. Gers, J. Schmidhuber, F. Cummins, Learning to forget: Continual prediction with lstm. *neural computation* 12(10): 2451-2471, *Neural Computation* 12 (10) (2000) 2451–2471